

Influence of length on acoustic time-of-flight (ToF) measurement on built in structures of Norway spruce timber

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Abstract: Time-of-flight (ToF) measurements were conducted on twelve 76x226 mm² cross-section 4.52 m in long specimens of Norway spruce timber pieces from a dismantled 19th century building in Barcelona (Catalonia, Spain). Two commercially available acoustic devices were used: the USLab ultrasound device with conical 22 and 45 kHz sensors, and the Microsecond Timer (MST) stress wave device with spike sensors. ToF were obtained for the full-length (4.52 m) specimens in an end-to-end arrangement and for lengths of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3 and 4 m on the same surface and on opposite surfaces. The differences between the velocities obtained from end-to-end and semi-direct measurements were less than 4.5%. Apparent velocity dependence on length was observed in short distance measurements. This can be corrected by determining a time lag (tL) from a linear regression between ToF and distance. Estimation of the modulus of elasticity (MOE) from the dynamic MOE (MOE_{dyn}) is acceptable ($r^2 = 0.45-0.69$) depending on the measurement procedure, and the best results for in-situ timber are obtained in edge surface velocity. Although MOR estimation from MOE_{dyn} improves slightly when knottiness is included, it has low predictive capacity.

Keywords: existing structures, non-destructive testing (NDT), sensors positioning, stress-wave, time lag (tL), time-of-flight (ToF), ultrasound wave

Introduction

The mechanical properties of structural timber can be estimated by acoustic wave measurements. This method is mainly used to predict the modulus of elasticity (MOE) through longitudinal time-of-flight (ToF) acoustic wave determination, which is influenced by several factors: moisture content (MC), temperature, size of the timber piece, test procedures, and the instruments used (James 1961; Gerhards 1982a; Bucur and Böhnke 1994; Wang 2013; Llana et al. 2014; Íñiguez-González et al. 2015; Llana et al. 2018). Several investigations focus on timber strength grading by acoustic methods (Arriaga et al. 2012; Casado et al. 2012; Pommier et al. 2013). Vega et al. (2012) found that the selection of piece length parameters can improve the prediction of mechanical properties.

Specimen geometry (cross-section size, length and ratios between their dimensions) and device frequency (in a dispersive medium) have a significant effect on wave propagation and acoustic velocity. The width-to-thickness ratio (w/th) of the timber piece cross-section influences longitudinal velocity; the higher the w/th ratio, the slower the velocity, but this change is small with length-to-width ratios (l/w) from 20 to 40 (Bucur 1984). Bartholomeu et al. (2003) studied the influence of cross-section size and length on ultrasonic measurements in *Eucalyptus sp.* specimens (instrument: Steinkamp BP7, Ultratest, Achim, Germany, with 45 kHz transducers) and concluded that a minimum specimen length should be specified, depending on the operating frequencies of the ultrasonic sensors used. The results were stable at length-to-wavelength ratios $l/\lambda > 5$. This requirement is included in the Brazilian non-destructive test standard NBR 15521 (2007). Oliveira et al. (2006) observed velocity variation in structural lumber of four wood species (*Pinus caribaea* Morelet., *Eucalyptus citriodora* Hook., *E. grandis* Hill. ex Maid. and *Hymenaea sp.*) with lengths ranging from 0.1 to 3 m at 22 kHz, and the $l/\lambda < 3$ was found to be negative, while the longitudinal velocity remained relatively stable at $l/\lambda > 3$. Divos et al. (2005) determined V_{long} in tapered pieces by the resonance-based acoustic method, with higher figures in the case of major tapers. Arriaga et

al. (2006) used ultrasound V_{long} data from a Sylvatest Duo (SylDuo) device (22 kHz) on 161 specimens of missanda (*Erythrophleum spp.*) and showed that length has a much greater influence than cross-section on ToF measurements. Apparent velocity decreased by 83 m s^{-1} as length increased by 1 m in the range of 1.6 m to 7.1 m (Arriaga et al. 2006). Íñiguez-González et al. (2007) studied the influence of specimen length and knottiness on ultrasound measurements (SylDuo device, 22 kHz) in Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.). For a 1 m length increase, the apparent velocity decreased by $68 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ in knot-free timber and 83 m s^{-1} in knotty timber. The influence of wood quality on ToF was also observed by Íñiguez-González et al. (2015). Arriaga et al. (2009) proposed some correction factors for ultrasound velocity in structural sawn Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), and Salzmänn pine (*Pinus nigra* ssp. *salzmannii* (Dunal) Franco) determined by the SylDuo. Wang (2013) studied the effect of cross-section size of square Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii* Mirb. Franco) on the dynamic modulus of elasticity (MOE_{dyn}), and advised against grading different sizes together and recommended instead appropriate MOE_{dyn} adjustments on account of the size effect.

This dependency of longitudinal velocity on length can be explained by a time lag (tL) effect on ToF measurements (Llana et al. 2013), which can be easily corrected by a simple adjustment (Llana et al. 2016). ToF is usually measured in end-to-end mode under laboratory conditions, but in the practical assessment of built-in structures, this approach is not feasible so that other sensor positions must be selected. In on-site inspections, sensors must be placed on the surfaces, i.e. either on the same surface or on surfaces opposite to each other. The effects of receiver sensor position were studied by Gerhards (1980, 1982b) and Arriaga et al. (2015). In particular, observations were made in the context of tL determination in case of radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmänn pine and maritime pine species by the SylDuo (22 kHz), USLab (45 kHz) and MST instruments (Arriaga et al. 2017).

Sound wave velocity is dependent on MOE_{dyn} and density, while Poisson's ratio also has a slight effect. It is generally accepted that the simplified 1D wave form equation for a

homogeneous and isotropic material describes adequately the wave behaviour of a timber.

Wood has a high attenuation rate and decreases wave energy to a greater extent at high frequencies. The signal may be reduced to an undetectable level. Stress waves and relatively low frequency ultrasound devices are therefore preferred for long timber pieces. High frequency transmissions are more sensitive to internal defects, and they are usually limited to short spans as the results are invalid for practical use in long pieces. On the other hand, low frequency transmissions have a lower attenuation effect and can span greater distances, although they are less sensitive to small defects within members (Kasal et al. 2010).

The present work examines the influence of distance in the determination of wave transmission velocity in in-situ ToF measurement performed with commercial devices on Norway spruce from existing (built-in) structures. MOE and MOR prediction based on MOE_{dyn} and knottiness will be analysed. It is intended to add information to existing data in order to elaborate an inspection protocol for built-in structures.

Material and methods

Material: Twelve large cross-section Norway spruce joist specimens from a dismantled 19th century building in the Sants-Montjuïc district of Barcelona (Catalonia, Spain) were tested. Their average dimensions were 4.52 m long and 76x226 mm² in cross-section. Each specimen was microscopically identified as Norway spruce [*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.] in the Forest Products Industries Laboratory of the School of Forest Engineering and Natural Resources, UPM (Madrid, Spain). Specimens were stored in the laboratory until a constant MC was achieved. Mean MC was determined by the oven-dry method according to standard EN 13183-1 (2002), using specimen slices free of knots and resin pockets according to EN 408 (2010+A1:2012). Average MC was 11.4% (CoV = 4.8%).

Time-of-flight (ToF) measurement: Two acoustic instruments were used: the USLab (Agricef, Campinas, Brazil) with conical 22 kHz and 45 kHz sensors; and the MicroSecond

Timer (MST) (Fakopp Enterprise Bt., Sopron, Hungary). The first one is based on ultrasonic measurements and excitation is induced by a piezoelectric sensor. The second one is a stress-wave device and excitation is induced by means of a hammer. Five different sensor placement arrangements were used (Figure 1): a) Direct mode (parallel to the axis of the piece) by placing sensors at each end of the specimen. Two ToF were registered at points separated at thirds of the width. The end-to-end or parallel velocity (V_0) was obtained by dividing the distance by the average ToF; In case of b) and c) surface measurements, both sensors are placed on the same edge and on the same face leading to surface velocities (V_{se} and V_{sf} , respectively); d) In the crossed measurements, a sensor is placed on one edge and the other one is placed on the opposite edge, leading to the crossed velocity from edge to opposite edge (V_{ce}); e) This is a crossed measurement by placing one sensor on one face and the other on the opposite face, leading to velocity data of V_{cf} .

Surface measurements were taken only on one edge and one face, which were chosen at random. The same is true for crossed measurements (one edge to the opposite edge and one face to the opposite face), in which the edge and face, where the emitter sensor was located, were chosen at random. In these setups, the sensors were placed at an angle equal to or slightly less than 45° with respect to the timber surface (Figure 1). Two measurement points were considered for each arrangement, located at thirds of the depth of the specimen. Exceptions are the edge measurements, where only one centred measurement was made due to narrowness. The mean value of both $h/3$ ToF measurement was considered in cases 1a, 1c, and 1e for calculation of velocity.

ToF (and velocity) in surface and crossed measurements were obtained for different lengths (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3 and 4 m). In the case of crossed measurements, these lengths correspond to slightly longer distances between sensors, because the lines joining the sensors form an angle with respect to the axis of the piece that varies from 24° to 1° .

MOE, MOR and density: The static modulus of elasticity (MOE) and the modulus of rupture (MOR) were determined by a 4-point edgewise bending test in accordance with European Standard EN 408 (2010+A1:2012) on simply supported timber pieces that were symmetrically loaded in bending at thirds of a span equal to 18 times the mean depth of the pieces (4068 mm). The value adopted for the shear modulus of elasticity was $G=\infty$, which means that MOE includes shear deflection effect. The MOE mean value was 10676 N mm^{-2} (CoV = 12.8%), and the MOR mean value was 41.4 N mm^{-2} (CoV = 27.2%), (Table 1). The density (ρ) and the MC were determined on specimen slices free of knots and resin pockets, according to EN 408 (2010+A1:2012) after mechanical testing. Density was obtained from the mass and volume of the slice, and it has a mean value of 417 kg m^{-3} (CoV = 8.3%), (Table 1).

Results and discussion

Visual strength grading

The visual grade was determined according to French standard NF B52001-1 (2011) for structural timber. This standard establishes 3 grades (ST-I, ST-II and ST-III) for Norway spruce, and 58% of pieces were rejected due to biological damage and distortions. Although biological damage is frequent and inevitable in built-in timber structures, it has little influence on mechanical properties provided it only affects some areas of the piece superficially (which was the case here). On the other hand, deformations (bow, spring and twist) and the presence of fissures have no significant influence on structural-size timber pieces (Esteban et al. 2010, Montón et al. 2015). Visual grading considering only the other specifications (ring growth, knots, resin pockets, slope of grain and waness) resulted in 0%, 67%, 25% and 8% of ST-I, ST-II, ST-III and rejected pieces, respectively (Table 1). Norway spruce grades ST-II and ST-III are assigned by the EN 1912 (2012) standard to strength classes C24 and C18, respectively, according to EN 338 (2016) with MOE mean values of 11000 and 9000 N mm^{-2} ,

MOR 5th percentiles of 24 and 18 N mm⁻² and a mean density of 420 and 380 kg m⁻³, respectively.

Knottiness and slope of grain

The timber visual grading process assesses knottiness, which is characterized by the concentrated knot diameter ratio (CKDR) (Divos and Tanaka 1997). The knot diameter ratio (KDR) is defined as the knot diameter divided by the width or thickness of the piece in the Japanese standard SIS-19 (1991). The CKDR is the sum of the 4 faces KDRs of the knots existing in any 150 mm length of a piece of timber. The distance defining a knot cluster is set at 150 mm by EN 844-9 (1997). The maximum CKDR observed on all 4 faces represents the quality of the piece, ranging from 0 to 1. In this work the CKDR value was obtained for the worst 150 mm section in the central segment of the piece with a length equal to 8 times the width of the beam (Table 1). This portion of the length is more representative of mechanical properties in bending (Arriaga et al. 2014). The tested specimens had a cut pattern which includes a radial face. Spike knots are present in radial faces although they are superficial with little influence on strength. They were therefore disregarded in CKDR evaluation. The general slope of grain was much lower than 1/14 (7%) in all specimens, which is the maximum allowed for the ST-I visual grade.

End to end measurements

The average value of velocity (V_0) of wave transmission for the 12 pieces was 6318, 6249 and 5634 m/s for USLab22, USLab45, and MST respectively, (Table 2). The values obtained with ultrasonic devices are slightly higher than obtained with the stress wave device, as was shown in previous works (Arriaga et al. 2017; Llana et al. 2018). The ratio between the velocities obtained with ultrasound (USLab45) and stress wave (MST) is 1.11. This ratio has a mean

value of 1.07 (1.06-1.09) in larger cross-section pieces of 4 coniferous species (Arriaga et al. 2017).

Surface measurements

The apparent surface velocity was obtained by dividing distances by ToF measurements made on the edge (V_{se}) and on the face (V_{sf}) surface of the piece (at lengths: 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0 m). The corresponding mean values are presented in Table 2. Figure 2 shows reciprocal X regression velocity vs length for all devices in surface measurements. As the P-value in the ANOVA is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between velocity and length at 95% confidence level. Length dependency is observed in short distances. A higher velocity was obtained in short distances for ultrasound; this tendency was also observed in previous works, and it was associated with timber singularities and the characteristics of the instrument used (Llana et al. 2016; Arriaga et al. 2017). On the other hand, a lower velocity seems to be obtained for stress wave over short distances.

Velocity dependence on length is due to a time lag (tL) in measured time that can be calculated from a linear regression $ToF = a + b l$ (Eq. 1), where b is the slope and a is the intersection point (tL) with the ordinates axis. This regression was made for length readings equal to or greater than 1.5 m, according to Arriaga et al. (2017), disregarding shorter lengths (0.5-1.0 m) in order to avoid local effects. High determination coefficients were obtained in all combinations ($r^2 = 0.98-0.99$), with 3 devices and 4 arrangements (edge and face surface and crossed measurements). Figure 3 shows an example for edge surface ToF with USLab 22 kHz device, where $a = -14.06 \mu s$. ToF should therefore be corrected by subtracting this tL to obtain the corrected velocity.

Corrected velocities were then obtained from ToF adjusted by the corresponding tL value. The velocity shows an approximately constant value for the four lengths in all combinations of devices and arrangements. There is no statistically significant relationship

between corrected velocity and length, at a confidence level of 95% (P-values – 0.23 to 0.97 - greater than 0.05), Figure 4.

Crossed measurements

Crossed velocity (apparent velocity) was obtained by dividing distances by ToF measurements made across the edges (V_{ce}) and the faces (V_{cf}) of the piece (at lengths: 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0 m). The distances were slightly longer than lengths because the lines joining the sensors form a certain angle with respect to the axis of the piece. The resulting mean values are presented in Table 2 and Figure 5 shows the reciprocal X regression velocity vs distance for all devices in crossed measurements. The P-values in the ANOVA are less than 0.05 except in two cases (across the faces with the USLab device at 22 and 45 kHz, with 0.10 and 0.92, respectively). There is therefore a statistically significant relationship between velocity and distance at 95% confidence level, although this is not clear in these two cases, showing lower velocity over short distances.

The tL was calculated according to Eq. (1) in a similar procedure to surface measurement, only considering in the linear regression the readings for distances equal to or greater than 1.5 m. High determination coefficients were obtained in all combined cases ($r^2=0.98-0.99$), with 3 devices and 2 arrangements (edge and face crossed measurements). The corrected velocities were then obtained by ToF adjusted by the corresponding tL value. The velocity shows a practically constant value for the four lengths in all combinations of devices and arrangements. There is no statistically significant relationship between corrected velocity and length, at a confidence level of 95% (P-values ≥ 0.05), Figure 6.

The values of the apparent velocities are converging with increasing distances, and this occurs for all devices and all measurement procedures. The corrected velocity has values close to those obtained for 4 m, with the exception of the crossed edge velocity that presents relatively higher values for the three devices (Figure 7). The velocity obtained with stress

wave is lower than that obtained by ultrasound devices (at a ratio around 0.91). This ratio was found to be 0.93-0.98 by Arriaga et al. (2017) in four pine species via USLab at 45 kHz.

The velocity difference between stress wave and ultrasound is mainly due to their different frequencies. In a dispersive medium such as wood, velocity depends on frequency (Bucur 2006). Moreover, the different procedures used by the device to detect signal arrival at the receiver sensor (stop timer thresholds) may also have an influence (Brashaw et al. 2005). Stress waves are generated in MST devices by hammer impact on the member detected by transducers. The resulting frequency depends on the weight of the hammer and the head material (Kasal et al. 2010). A wave-front with several frequencies is generated by impact. The frequency that is detected on arrival depends on the dimensions of the piece of timber and its length, although it is a far lower frequency than the one corresponding to an ultrasonic device. The velocities corrected with the tL are very close to the velocities obtained directly at 4 m length (with differences of less than 5%). The mean ratio between the velocity for 4 m length and V_{corr} is similar in all cases (0.98), except in the case of cross measurements between edges (1.05). Such differences were not observed by Arriaga et al. (2017), but it should be taken into account that the slenderness of the cross-section dimensions of timber pieces was different (width/thickness = 2.89, in this work and 1.55 in the previous one). Cross-section slenderness has some influence on velocity; the higher the slenderness the lower the velocity (Bucur 2006). The velocity differences between obtained by end-to-end measurements and surface or crossed measurements are equal to or less than 4.5%, which is similar to results obtained by Arriaga et al. (2017).

Dynamic modulus of elasticity

The MOE_{dyn} was obtained according to Eq. (2), where V_i is the velocity obtained for the different procedures (V_0 , V_{se} , V_{sf} , V_{ce} and V_{cf}) and ρ_i is the density of each piece. Surface and

crossed velocities were obtained from 4 m length measurements, including and excluding the tL correction of ToF. $MOE_{dyn} = V_i^2 \cdot \rho_i$ (Eq. 2)

MOE prediction and influence of method on velocity measurement

The important question here centers on the most appropriate velocity for in-situ readings. It is not generally feasible to measure end-to-end velocity in built-in structures due to the impossibility of accessing piece ends. It should therefore be a velocity based on measurements of ToF on the surface or crossed measurements (semi-direct paths). In these measurements, tL correction in the ToF could be applied, which would lead to a more precise corrected velocity value. However, this has the disadvantage of requiring several readings per piece, increasing on-site execution time. It therefore seems that the most suitable procedure for built-in structures would be to measure ToF at the longest possible distance (in this case 4 m) on the surface of the piece or crosswise between faces or edges. This would not require correction by tL due to the small influence of length on long sections. To find out how to obtain the velocity that is most representative of the properties of timber pieces, linear regressions were applied between MOE and MOE_{dyn} to analyze whether or not there are significant differences between the different procedures: $MOE = a + b MOE_{dyn}$ (Eq. 3). Results are shown in Table 3.

There is a statistically significant relationship between MOE and MOE_{dyn} , at a confidence level of 95% (P-values < 0.05). Firstly, it can be seen that including the tL correction in 4 m ToF does not improve the prediction of MOE compared to the uncorrected measurements. Secondly, it can be deduced that prediction using end-to-end velocity is not better than prediction using semi-direct velocity, except the case of the MST. Finally, the procedure that presents the highest coefficient of determination and the smallest standard error of estimation is the one based on the ToF measurement along the edge surface.

Furthermore, this is usually the best accessible surface for in-situ assessment. Table 4 shows

the average MOE/MOE_{dyn} ratios for each device and procedure. This ratio was obtained in a previous work in 4 coniferous species, with mean values of 0.719 and 0.805 for the USLab at 45 kHz and MST, respectively. These values are close to those obtained in this work.

MOR prediction

MOR prediction is much poorer than MOE prediction. This is because the bending strength of a piece depends strongly on defects that appear locally in a piece (mainly knot size and position and slope of grain) and it is harder to evaluate. The linear regression between MOR and MOE_{dyn} results in lower r^2 : $MOR = a + b MOE_{dyn}$ (Eq. 4). Table 5 shows the coefficients of these regressions ($r^2 = 0.15 - 0.33$) from MOE_{dyn} obtained by surface edge velocity. There is no statistically significant relationship between MOR and MOE_{dyn} at a confidence level of 95% (P-values ≥ 0.05).

Solid wood testing can be performed via the shadow and propagation velocity technique. The first measures the energy loss that occurs when the wave changes medium through defects (by reflection and dispersion). The second, which is used here, measures signal propagation time instead of damping, so that it is less dependent on local defects. The inclusion of the knottiness parameter (CKDR) in the regression slightly increases the predictive power (Eq. 5 and Table 6): $MOR = a + b MOE_{dyn} + c CKDR$ (Eq. 5). However, there is no statistically significant relationship between MOR and MOE_{dyn} + CKDR at a confidence level of 95% (P-values ≥ 0.05).

The consideration of the CKDR together with the MOE_{dyn} in the estimation of the MOR improves predictive power (r^2 0.33 to 0.40, 0.23 to 0.34, and 0.15 to 0.32 for USLab22, USLab45 and MST respectively, without tL correction). This is consistent with similar works performed with the same acoustic methods in different coniferous species, showing increasing r^2 from 0.60 to 0.66 (Iñiguez 2007), and from 0.40 to 0.46 (Montón 2012).

In previous works similar results were obtained. The coefficient of determination for the MOR estimation from MOE_{dyn} was 0.61 in the test of coniferous sawn timber pieces with a cross-section from 150x200 to 200x250 and 4.1-5.6 m long; and it increased to 0.65 when CKDR was included (Arriaga et al. 2012). Similarly, $r^2 = 0.46-0.50$ were obtained in Radiata pine (*Pinus radiata* D. Don) in 80x120 mm cross-section 2.5 m long pieces, and it improved to 0.50-0.54 when CKDR was included (Arriaga et al. 2014). Nevertheless, the present work results in a lower prediction of MOR. It is very difficult to evaluate the defects that reduce the strength of a timber piece, and this leads to a high level of variability in the results.

Conclusions

The effect of length on velocity can be corrected by consideration of the time lag. Time-of-flight should be taken at different distances over the length of the piece, from a minimum of the order of 1.5 m to the longest possible distance, after which time lag should be obtained. Time lag corrected velocities differ from non-corrected velocities by 2%-4% for ultrasound devices and 1% for stress wave device in edge surface procedures. These differences increase to 4%-9% and 2%, respectively, in MOE determination. The estimation error for mechanical properties is therefore practically negligible for the stress wave device (MST) and it is lower than 9% for the ultrasound device (USLab). The differences between the velocities obtained from end-to-end and semi-direct measurements (superficial and crossed) amount to less than 4.5%, which is similar to data found in previous works. The estimation of the static modulus of elasticity from a linear regression with the MOE_{dyn} is relatively good. The coefficient of determination varies depending on the procedure used to measure time-of-flight ($r^2 = 0.45-0.69$). The procedure with the greatest predictive capacity for in-situ timber is the one that determines superficial velocity in the edge. The estimation of bending strength based on linear regression based on MOE_{dyn} has a low predictive power. The results are slightly better when

the degree of knottiness is added. The ratio between MOE_{stat} and MOE_{dyn} is device dependent: 0.68, 0.74 and 0.86 for the 22 kHz USLab, 45 kHz USLab, and MST devices, respectively.

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Tables

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties, moisture content, knottiness and visual grade.

Specimen	MC %	MOE N mm ⁻²	MOR N mm ⁻²	ρ kg m ⁻³	Grade	CKDR
1	11.2	7042	14.4	391	R	0.20
2	11.9	11323	43.1	426	ST-III	0.11
3	10.9	10398	27.2	400	ST-III	0.11
4	11.7	12384	44.8	416	ST-II	0.07
5	11.8	11118	50.3	407	ST-II	0.07
6	10.9	11107	56.8	439	ST-II	0.12
7	11.0	10858	46.0	412	ST-II	0.12
8	11.4	10297	48.2	399	ST-II	0.12
9	11.0	10246	40.3	391	ST-II	0.18
10	11.5	10539	48.6	383	ST-III	0.06
11	12.7	10364	39.5	428	ST-II	0.12
12	11.0	12436	38.2	513	ST-II	0.07
Mean	11.4	10676	41.4	417		0.11
CoV	4.8	12.8	27.2	8.3		38.5

Grade: visual grade according to NF B52001-1 (2011) standard not considering biological damage, distortion and fissures (R = rejected). CKDR: Concentrated Knot Diameter Ratio in the central segment of 8h length, being h the depth.

Table 2. Mean values of apparent velocities (m s⁻¹) for each length and device.

L (m)	USLab 22 kHz				USLab 45 kHz				MST			
	V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}	V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}	V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}
0.5	6786	6950	3985	6087	6664	6817	3972	6094	4958	5090	3056	4455
1.0	6496	6521	5256	6375	6461	6511	5234	6363	5136	5225	4246	4994
1.5	6401	6457	5703	6378	6367	6446	5784	6396	5302	5326	4811	5180
2.0	6365	6420	5963	6348	6331	6349	5953	6322	5331	5360	5065	5231
3.0	6299	6304	6127	6270	6240	6202	6092	6153	5403	5424	5297	5295
4.0	6201	6206	6125	6177	5959	5983	6048	5934	5381	5421	5351	5349
V _{corr}	6077	6056	6397	6053	5731	5725	6214	5671	5445	5492	5745	5466
V ₀	6318				6249				5634			

V_{corr} mean value of velocity obtained with ToF corrected by time lag (tL); V₀ mean value of velocity obtained from end to end

Table 3. Linear regression coefficients, Equation (3), MOE vs MOE_{dyn} for each velocity detection procedure and for each device.

Instrument, data	V ₀	MOE _{dyn} obtained from different velocities								
		at L = 4 m				at L = 4 m with tL correction				
		V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}	V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}	
USLab22	a	3279	3224	3184	3171	3507	3158	3106	3286	3441
	b	0.4421	0.4623	0.4641	0.4777	0.4482	0.4872	0.4945	0.4349	0.4727
	r ²	0.62	0.66	0.63	0.56	0.61	0.66	0.63	0.56	0.61
	StE	887	834	873	954	898	837	876	952	900
	P val.	0.0024	0.0013	0.0021	0.0054	0.0028	0.0013	0.0021	0.0051	0.0028
USLab45	a	4807	4431	4758	3942	4081	4270	4601	4017	3915
	b	0.3577	0.4185	0.3933	0.4388	0.4461	0.4708	0.4446	0.4141	0.5052
	r ²	0.53	0.64	0.59	0.59	0.62	0.69	0.59	0.59	0.62
	StE	979	863	913	918	881	864	915	917	884
	P val.	0.0070	0.0018	0.0033	0.0035	0.0023	0.0018	0.0034	0.0035	0.0023
MST	a	2810	3935	4187	4256	4012	3965	4223	4456	4081
	b	0.5916	0.5555	0.5266	0.5352	0.5556	0.5424	0.5117	0.4531	0.5263
	r ²	0.63	0.54	0.50	0.45	0.52	0.54	0.50	0.45	0.53
	StE	877	975	1012	1067	989	974	1011	1067	988
	P val.	0.022	0.0066	0.0098	0.0175	0.0077	0.0066	0.0098	0.0175	0.0077

a: coefficient of Eq. 3 in N mm⁻²; b: coefficient of Eq. 3; StE: standard error of estimation in N mm⁻²

Table 4. Average MOE/MOE_{dyn} ratios for each velocity detection procedure and for each device without and with tL correction.

Instru- ments		Average MOE/MOE _{dyn} ratios obtained from different velocities								
		V ₀	at L = 4 m w/o tL correction				at L = 4 m with tL correction			
			V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}	V _{se}	V _{sf}	V _{ce}	V _{cf}
USLab22	Ratio	0.641	0.666	0.664	0.682	0.671	0.695	0.700	0.630	0.701
	CoV %	8.7	8.5	8.6	9.3	9.1	8.5	8.5	9.3	9.1
USLab45	Ratio	0.658	0.722	0.717	0.700	0.728	0.791	0.789	0.669	0.803
	CoV %	12.8	9.8	10.6	9.5	9.9	9.6	10.4	9.6	9.7
MST	Ratio	0.805	0.885	0.871	0.894	0.895	0.868	0.852	0.782	0.857
	CoV %	8.5	10.3	10.2	10.6	9.7	10.3	10.2	10.7	9.8

Table 5. Linear regression coefficients of Eq. 4 (without consideration of CKDR) and Eq. 5 (with consideration of CKDR) in plots MOR vs MOE_{dyn} for surface edge velocity (V_{se}) procedure without (w/o) and with tL correction at L = 4 m.

Instru- ments, data		V _{se} procedure Without CKDR		V _{se} procedure CKDR considered	
		w/o tL	with tL	w/o tL	with tL
		USLab22	<i>a</i>	-2.1	-2.3
<i>b</i>	0.00270		0.00283	0.001772	0.001844
<i>c</i>	0.33		0.33	-85.09	-86.08
<i>r</i> ²	9.6		9.7	0.40	0.40
<i>StE</i>	0.0495		0.0512	9.6	9.7
<i>P val.</i>	10.2		9.7	0.0998	0.1014
USLab45	<i>a</i>	0.00209	0.00234	38.8	38.9
	<i>b</i>	0.24	0.23	0.000989	0.001085
	<i>c</i>	10.3	10.4	-107.96	-109.01
	<i>r</i> ²	0.1096	0.1132	0.34	0.34
	<i>StE</i>	11.7	11.7	10.1	10.1
	<i>P val.</i>	0.00245	0.00240	0.1516	0.1531
MST	<i>a</i>	0.15	0.16	50.2	50.1
	<i>b</i>	10.8	10.9	0.000503	0.000496
	<i>c</i>	0.2057	0.2045	-131.78	-131.63
	<i>r</i> ²			0.32	0.31
	<i>StE</i>			10.3	10.3
	<i>P val.</i>			0.1835	0.1834

a, *c*: coefficients of eq. 4 in N mm⁻²; *b*: coefficient of E; Eq. 4;
StE: standard error of estimation in N mm⁻²